

Criterion Performance Physical Fitness Components Relation with Sprinting Performance

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was Criterion Performance Physical Fitness Components Relation with Sprinting Performance. The 150 male Sprinters were selected Inter- University representation in the academic year of 2015-2016, 2016-2017 and 2018-19 in Andhra Pradesh non-randomly by purposive sample was used. Karl Pearson coefficient of correlation was used to Analysis of the collected data on Criterion Performance Physical Fitness Components were Complex reaction ability (0.585*), Movement Speed (0.339*), Acceleration ability(0.462*),Locomotor Speed (0.371*),Speed Endurance(0.379*), Agility (0.299*), Coordination (0.573*), Explosive Strength(0.565*), Dynamic Balance(0.364*),Dynamic Flexibility (0.259*) and Strength Endurance (0.289*)coefficient of correlation with Sprinting Performancehad been positively with significant level 0.05.Remaining Performance Physical FitnessComponentsdid not correlate on this current study.**Key words:** Performance Physical Fitness, Components, Sprinters, Athletics.

Introduction

From the earliest time running has been a natural part of man's existence. One of the earliest examples of competitive running can be found in the work of Homer, who tells of races ran in the 12th century BC. Thus, man has been racing on foot for over three thousand years (Blacklock and Kennett, 2000). It was expected that children with a more extended training history would exhibit more pronounced anthropometric, physical fitness and motor coordination profiles matching the specific sport (Blacklock and Kennett, 2000).

In athletics and track and field, sprints (or dashes) are races over short distances. They are among the oldest running competitions. A rapid movement from one place to another place is required in many athletic activities especially in sprint running (kukolj, Ropret, Ungarkovic and Jaric,2001; Pinero et al,2010). Sprinting is an ancient event in athletics starting in the first Greece

Olympic Games and it is a human ability to perform a maximum running velocity (Haneda, Enomoto, Hogo and Fujii, 2003). At the professional level, sprinters begin the race by assuming a crouching position in the starting blocks before leaning forward and gradually moving into an upright position as the race progresses and momentum is gained. The set position differs depending on the start. Body alignment is of key importance in producing the optimal amount of force. Ideally the athlete should begin in a four-point stance and push off using both legs for maximum force production. Athletes remain in the same lane on the running track throughout all sprinting events with the sole exception of the 400 m indoors. Races up to 100 m are largely focused upon acceleration to an athlete's maximum speed. All sprints beyond this distance increasingly incorporate an element of endurance (Pintero et al, 2010).

The performance of players is influenced by many factors such as physical, physiological and psychological variables, technique, tactics, physique, body size, body composition and application of biomechanical principles (Ortega et al., 2008). No doubt the performance of player influenced by many factors but still Physical fitness components is the primary factor among these entire factors.

Fitness is a condition in which an individual has sufficient energy to avoid fatigue and enjoy life. It is necessary for elderly people to maintain and improve their physical fitness in order to satisfy healthy, high quality of daily life (Tanaka et al., 2004) [9]. Skill related physical fitness refers to an individual's athletic ability in sports such as tennis and encompasses skill-related attributes like dynamic balance, power, speed and agility; the health-related aspect is a measure of cardiovascular endurance, muscle strength, endurance and flexibility and body composition (Hopkins & Walker, 1988). The present study therefore aims to study the relationship of criterion performance physical fitness components association with Sprinting performance.

Methodology

Purpose of the Study: This study would be decided the Criterion Performance Physical Fitness Components Relation with Sprinting Performance.

Selection of the Subjects: 150 male Sprinters were selected Inter- University representation in the academic year of 2015-2016, 2016-2017 and 2018-19 in Andhra Pradesh State on non-randomly by purposive sample had been used.

Figure-I
Performance Physical Fitness Components

S. No	Performance Physical Fitness Components	Test
1	Complex Reaction Ability	Nelson Reaction Test
2	Movement Speed	20mts Run
3	Acceleration Ability	50mts Run
4	Locomotor Speed	30mts Run
5	Speed Endurance	300mts Run
6	Agility	Shuttle Run
7	Coordination	Baseball Throw
8	Explosive Strength	Standing Broad Jump
9	Dynamic Balance	Balance Test
10	Dynamic Flexibility	Flexibility Test
11	Strength Endurance	Push Ups
12	Simple Reaction Ability	Nelson Reaction Test
13	Endurance	600 Yard Run
14	Static Flexibility	Sit and Reach Test
15	Maximum Strength	1rm Test

Collection of the Data and Tools

The data had been collected by administrating the standard procedures for taking performance physical fitness components as well as Sprinters performance and tools were used stopwatches, push up stands, spirometer and Flexible measuring tape for flexibility. The score had been recorded time in the nearest one tenth of the seconds and nearest centimetres.

Statistical Analysis and Discussions

In order to find out the relationship of criterion performance physical fitness components with Sprinting performance with the Karl Pearson coefficient of correlation had been used and testing the Hypothesis the level of confidence is 0.05.

Figure-II: Criterion Performance Physical Fitness Components Association with Sprinting Performance

S. No	Performance Physical Fitness Components	Coefficient of Correlation 'r'
1	Complex reaction ability	0.585*
2	Movement Speed	0.339*
3	Acceleration ability	0.462*
4	Locomotor Speed	0.371*
5	Speed Endurance	0.379*
6	Agility	0.299*
7	Coordination	0.573*
8	Explosive Strength	0.565*
9	Dynamic Balance	0.364*
10	Dynamic Flexibility	0.259*
11	Strength Endurance	0.289*
12	Simple reaction ability	0.234
13	Endurance	0.198
14	Static flexibility	0.212
15	Maximum strength	0.197

N=150, $r_{0.05(150)}=0.238$, *Significant at 0.05 level.

An analysis of the above table reveals that Sprinters had been significantly related to criterion performance physical fitness components were Complex reaction ability (0.585*), Movement Speed (0.339*), Acceleration ability(0.462*),Locomotor Speed (0.371*),Speed Endurance (0.379*), Agility (0.299*), Coordination (0.573*), Explosive Strength (0.565*), Dynamic Balance(0.364*),Dynamic Flexibility (0.259*) and Strength Endurance (0.289*) as obtained values of correlation were greater than the value of $r= 0.238$ the correlation to be significant at 0.05 performance physical fitness components were Endurance, Maximum Strength, Static Flexibility, Simple reaction ability and endurance as their correlation values are less than the value of $r=0.238$ need for significance at 0.05 level of confidence.

Figure-III:Criterion Performance Physical Fitness Components Relation with Sprinting Performance

As for the results finally, the study exposes that Sprinting performance would be significantly related to criterion performance physical fitness components were Complex reaction ability (0.585*), Movement Speed (0.339*), Acceleration ability(0.462*),Locomotor Speed (0.371*),Speed Endurance (0.379*), Agility (0.299*), Coordination (0.573*), Explosive Strength (0.565*), Dynamic Balance(0.364*),Dynamic Flexibility (0.259*) and Strength Endurance (0.289*). As per the analysis,suggestion to the coaches, physical directors, physical education teachers, physical instructors to concentrate on the above criterion performance physical fitness components while selecting or screening for Sprinters in a basic level. It would be given effective and good performance in a specific competition.

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